

Development Partners Activities on Students Learning Outcomes in Basic Education Schools of Rwanda: A Case of Kicukiro District

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Abstract: The study intended to evaluate the contribution of development partners' activities on students learning outcomes in Basics Education Public Schools of Kicukiro District-Rwanda. Specifically, this research assessed the effect of development partners in basic education public schools in Kicukiro District, Rwanda; to assess the level of learning outcomes in basic education public schools in Kicukiro, Rwanda; the researcher adopted the descriptive survey design with quantitative and qualitative methods of collection and analyzing data. The study population comprised 272 from which a sample size of 162 was determined using Yamane formula including 154 teachers, and 8 head teacher and local leaders. The researcher used simple randomly sampling to select the teachers of basic education public schools, and purposively for selecting head teachers and sector educational officials. This study used the questionnaire and interview guide to gather information. Information was analysed descriptively in the term of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation correlational analysis was given by multiple regression through statistical product and service solution. The findings showed that there were effects of the development partners in the promotion of the learning outcomes of the students in basic education schools and confirmed by 54.5% responded agree and 30% responded strongly agree that development partners provide seminars to child right awareness, education fund for teaching, respondents also confirmed that developments partners activities have increased the performance of students and learning outcome at higher level in basic education schools by providing services that boost education outcomes through teaching and learning materials such as education technology devices like computers, tablets, internet, e-books, and train the users how to use them in basic education schools of Rwanda. The researcher recommended that the Ministry of Education should use different strategies to mobilize developments partners and allocate them with the areas of priorities; the district of Kicukiro through the department partners "JADF" should identify the areas that need focus before allowing them engaging in the activities.

Keywords: Development partners' activities, Students learning outcomes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development partners such as Nongovernmental organization (NGOs) were basic institutions in educational development. NGO do not only working with the society in developmental programs but fortify young leaders in environmental sustainable development. Furthermore development partners usually include university students in learning process to educational outcome and young persons and young person's passion and inventiveness for sustainable education. Development partner's activities may be helpful in compensating the restricted financial means and providing learners lessons, teaching and learning resources, and capacity development in education development (Wiek, 2016).

According to Nomura and Abe (2001), learners had ameliorated next thinking where learners stated their concerns about most of ongoing problems in Vietnam like dishonesty, changing climate, food security, environment degradation and social alienation for youths to be affected by non-communicable diseases (Nomura & Abe, 2001).

The development partners, in the raising of the quality education activities make people grow and raised rational and action oriented for learners know the expectation more environment friendly attitude. One of the young people in the basic education schools of Vietnam reported; the appreciation of distressing collective effects of social and environmental issues via the skills I gained from the basic education schools. The young person kept reporting, youth would reorganize their living conditions and stimulate every persons among them to preserve every beautiful place through the promoting of the quality education and education outcomes” (Bhandari & Abe, 2001).

In Rwanda, development partners activities contributes to the child education systems from the bottom up, starting with families and community-based groups that are linked to support when needed at township and state/ division levels. In the realm of Education, this is done mainly through Child Protection Groups (CPGs) formed at the community level to take practical steps to manage and resolve cases of abuse, exploitation, neglect and violence and advocate for the best interests of the children involved. Through the Rwandan CPGs, children, village authorities and adults from communities discuss and manage children’s affairs and contribute to the deterrence of drug abuse or children’s protection within the society as well as at the township level and strengthens quality education for the education outcomes. To strengthen the response to quality education and child protection cases, the basic education schools in Rwanda have been uplifted by some development partners’ activities (Miwa, 2003).

1.1 Problem statement

Development partners activities which strive to improve the development of world and less developed countries via quality education like the provision of training and capacity building of teaching staff members leaners, school principals and local managers, parents to positively attain higher level of discipline, child protection and child rights. However, in 2016, the report done by development partner such as Save the Children to Rwandan educational system in its 5 years project program of Mureke Dusome shows that the Rwandan education need a lot of effort and partnership to provide educational qualify outcomes, and standards required to the labor market owing to the detail that children complete their basic education schools without even having the basic skills on literacy and numeracy. This report shows that basic competences are the key to educational development and if children miss the basic education faces much challenge that hamper them to continue their further studies such as university and other higher learning institutions (Save the Children (Mureke Dusome, 2016). It was in this regard that the study necessitates evaluating effects development partners’ activities to increase quality education in basic education schools in Rwanda through its deferent outreach activities.

1.2 Objectives

This research evaluated the contribution of development partners’ activities on students learning outcomes within basics education schools, specifically assessed the effects of development partners in basic education public schools in Rwanda, and the level of learning outcomes in basic education schools of Rwanda.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This research will be useful to the Ministry of health, higher learning institutions and public secondary schools, NGOs and the entire local community. The study findings will guide all partners and practitioners in educational sector to ameliorate educational quality and learning outcomes for educational development. This research will also give evidences on the quality assurance and standard officers in their guiding and managerial responsibilities to improve education outcomes. This research may service as the basis for suitable research on impact of development partners on educational development in Rwanda.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The researcher has reviewed the previous studies done on development partners and outcomes.

2.1 Effects of Development Partners in Basic Education Public Schools

The development partners measured and extended education quality for development partners in most of large than academic performance of students. Acquiring cognitive and non-cognitive capacities by students, a pertinent local involvement association, pertinent and conceptuality of educational activities were taken into consideration for quality measurements (Horton, 2003).

Horton, (2003) argued that all the development partners followed local involvement as the national bank for improving educational quality. Parental involvement in managing schools improves school responsiveness and high level of school attendance and students. Development partners evidenced that local asset and personnel untruth wider and would be gathered as would asset from Panchayati Raj Organization. Development partner's approaches fortify the role of school based model to educational quality increase and he desire for decentralization assist organization. Head Teachers were taken into consideration to be pertinent for adjustment. Public institutions for creating and fortifying schools at local community. Development partners to construct abilities to assess and identify their projects. Development partners had presented new terms of education quality, they may stimulated option and instruments for assessing quality in academic performance (Brinkerhoff, 2007).

Development partner's approaches may not be attained without educational follow up or supplementary policy adjusts. Development partners founded the term of volunteering and challenges by teachers' absence and making adequate learning outcome for students.

MacAbbey, (2007) said that as public institutions used different development partners approaches to discourse management and finance constraints. Wide community teaching staff members were welcomed with payment of wages of fixed teaching staff. This research, while acknowledging provision a reduced amount of educational facilities and unskilled teaching staff members (Wood and MacAbbey, 2007).

2.2 Empirical Literature

The centrality of development partners to education outcomes and development in the process of any country development might not be immediately exaggerated particularly in primary and secondary education. Therefore, public institutions were gradually improving its venture in educational activities, necessities and needs of education was developed. School facilities were not enough to accommodate all children in schooling age. There is a need of adequate and conducive organization with appropriate educational requirements which can raise the quality of education.

Development partners' activities had to involve learners in delighted actions and attempt to develop education in rural area and employing new pedagogical approaches. Learners must be able to read and write and ameliorate cognitive and non-cognitive behavior in order to facilitate students to complete their studies. In this regard, public institution must provide all necessitate and conducive educational environment to attain the expected target and attain high quality of learning outcome such as training teachers for better teaching methodologies (NGOs, 2016).

2.3 Development Partners for Basic Education Public Schools

Government and benefices with partners have the responsibilities such as improving collaboration and coordination of the educational activities aiming at improving education outcomes; many development partners letter for some struggle among Non-Government Organization in similar regions and project.

Therefore, design process development partner's actions were detained in region and community leaders were often to take part in education planning and management. De development partners, thus, argue that cooperating with public institution was ameliorated. Most of them lead to clear collaboration with MINEDUC: nonappearance of evidently describe policies based on funders, inadequate professional abilities in the ministry, poor definition of policies and outline for public-private development partner's collaboration (Kadzamira, 2002).

2.4 Educational Capacity Development on Level of Students Learning Outcomes

Capacity development in education was fascinating are in term of adjusting support building. Consuming past was very pertinent for training, development partners to be able to produce effect on training.

Kasturi Sen (2006), in his study, the education and country development, gives suitable recap of adjustment stated. The approach based on Paris Declaration focuses on the necessity to fortify the state and organization in the 20 years ago of reducing public sector via policies and educational sector. During this time, training and professional development took into account the role of development partners and other NGOs. However, recent transition in donor policy in educational sector was regressive to help for public institutions and private sector to consolidate their pertinence in education development, the term capacity development itself possess an intention to invigorate and expand NGO activities in educational sector with the association between NGOs and capacity or professional development in education has raised its concentration in e education actions (Paris Declaration, 2006).

Therefore, prior taking into accounting education studies, it was very crucial to provide term, nature and story of capacity development according to partners and infer some alternatives. Capacity development was seen as a long term, internal procedure of ameliorating durable capacity on personal, organization and system. This correlated to and had effects for development partner's actions in four various ye independent ways.

2.5 Constructivism theory

As revised and recapitulated by Powell and Kalina (2009), the constructivism theory ensures that children are born with knowledge or they acquire it after they are born. The theory indicates that through the integration of teaching and learning materials, children acquire new knowledge and skills. This shows that children with disabilities learn and develop their skills well if they are included in the same class with their colleagues without disabilities because they feel supported and warm rather than integrating them in their own isolated classrooms. This means that interaction opportunities offered by development partners are cognitively beneficial for students' outcomes, with no collateral damage for the academic development of their typically developing classmates.

This theory explains how a person internalizes culture or general conducive and education and teaching take place. According to theory Vygotsky, complex learning environments, social negotiations and respect for multiple opinions, student ownership of learning and common ground for knowledge construction are important factors in a learning environment. The aspects of the theory are reflected in and inform the various teaching methods like active learning, inquiry, discovery learning, cooperative and problem based learning with competences. Development partners contribute to the trainings on teaching methodologies to teachers in schools and colleges could also improve the student's outcomes in schools (Fearn & Howard, 2012).

In a view of that, the theory clearly demonstrates that when development partners actively engage in the provision of teaching and learning inputs and investing in capacity building of the educators, can influence their learning and raise learning effectively.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Kombo and Tromp (2006) describe the study plan as expected or plan that was to produce responses to the study issues. The study design pinpoints may be considered as planning process in gathering and presenting information with the intention to put together pertinence based on study objectives. The researcher adopted quantitative and qualitative methods to get the required information for the study. The researcher used descriptive statistics and themes for presenting the findings of the study.

3.1 Target Population and Sample Size

A study done by Burns and Grove (2003) refers the target population persons that fulfill the requirement for inclusion to the study process. Therefore, Kicukiro District is one among 3 districts of City of Kigali which has approximately 1460 teachers of basic education public schools, 61 head teachers and 10 education local leaders in 10 sectors. The researcher purposively selected 2 sectors; Kicukiro and Kanombe sectors with 8 head teachers and local leaders in charge of education, and 154 teaching staff members of Kicukiro District.

3.2 Sampling Technique

According to Frankel and Wallen (1990), the term sampling technique refers to process adopted to choose some components in such way that they stand for the present features of the entire population of the study. In addition, Kombo and Tromp (2006) indicate that sampling technique is the process of choosing members from the entire subjects or objects of the research that sampled one encapsulates features found for entire population. Therefore, a sampled refers to a finite element of statistical population whose characteristics were assessed to obtain relevant data. When dealing with the persons it may be described as a group of respondents obtained from the general population with the aim to examine it. This research chose teachers using simple random sampling and the local leaders with head teachers using purposive sampling.

3.3 Data Collection Tools

The current research intends to evaluate contribution of development partners' activities on students learning outcomes in Basics Education Public Schools of Kicukiro District-Rwanda. The researcher used questionnaire survey and interviews

A questionnaire was distributed to respondents for obtaining relevant data as asserted by Kothari (2004). Questionnaire was pertinent for gathering responses from teachers and which was organized and self-distributed to respondents. The researcher designed questionnaire for teachers of basic education schools of Kicukiro. A well-structured questionnaire was administered to different respondents whose views, ideas and attitudes concerning development partners impact on education outcomes.

Furthermore, the researcher held interviews with local leaders and school principals depending on their availability due to many responsibilities. Therefore, it was utilized to acquire relevant data. The intention to supplement information that was collected using questionnaire survey.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

The researcher shows the distribution of 154 teachers and 8 head teachers and local dedication leaders from selected sectors and schools of Kicukiro District whose information was basing on their gender characteristics. The statistics shows that during the study, all 154 respondents were educated from secondary certificate to master's level. The tallies shows that 28 respondents equivalent to 17% were holders of secondary certificates, 43 respondents equivalent to 27% were holders of diploma in education, the majority of the respondents were 81 equivalent to 51% holders of bachelor degree in education while only 10 respondents equivalent to 5% were holders of master's degree. This means that all the respondents were qualified to teach in basic education including primary levels and secondary levels.

4.1 Presentation of the Findings

In this section, the researcher presents the findings analyzed from the primary data collected from the selected schools of Kicukiro district on the contribution of the development partners on students learning outcomes in basic education schools. The data were analyzed and presented according to their objectives which are: to assess effects of development partners in basic education public schools, to assess the level of learning outcomes in basic education public schools, to identify the influence of development partners activities in the students learning outcomes in basic education public schools of Kicukiro, Rwanda.

4.2 Teachers' Responses on the effects of development partners in education

During the study the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the 154 respondents who were present in the research. The data were analyzed and presented according to the first objective talking about the assess effects of development partners in basic education public schools of Kicukiro, Rwanda.

Table 1: The effects of development partners in basic education

Statement	St. Dis		Dis		Neut		Agr		St. Ag	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Regular training to facilitate the lesson in teaching	2	1.3	5	3	17	11	84	54.5	46	30
Donate schools teaching and learning materials	20	13	5	3	20	13	64	41.5	45	29
Development partners provision of seminars to child right awareness	6	3.8	6	3.8	15	9.7	93	60	34	22
Provision of education fund for teaching	1	0.6	32	20.7	9	5.8	88	57	24	15
Provision of professional training	3	2	11	7.1	5	3.2	73	47	62	41
Mean	5	3	11.8	8	13.2	8.6	80.4	52.2	42.2	27.4

Source: Primary Data (2023).

The table 1 describes the effects of the development partners in the promotion of the learning outcomes of the students in basic education schools of Kicukiro District, Rwanda where the majority of the respondents agreed that there were positive effects in the provision of the development partner practices to boost education. As to whether the development partners provide regular training to facilitate the lesson in teaching and learning, 54.5% responded agree and 30% responded strongly agree, the minority were in disagreement side. They were asked if the development partners donate schools teaching and learning materials, 41.5% responded agree and 29% responded strongly agree, the minority were in disagreement side. They were asked if the development partners provide seminars to child right awareness, 60% responded agree and 22% responded strongly agree, while the minority were in disagreement side. They were asked if the development partners provide education fund for teaching, 57% responded agree and 15% responded strongly agree, while the minority were in disagreement side. They were asked if the development partners provide education fund for teaching, 57% responded agree and 15% responded strongly agree, while the minority were in disagreement side.

According to Fowler (2000), the development partners' activities had to involve learners in delighted actions and attempt to develop education in rural area and employing new pedagogical approaches. Learners must be able to read and write and ameliorate cognitive and non-cognitive behavior in order to facilitate students to complete their studies.

4.3 Assessing the level of learning outcomes in basic education schools

Table 2: the level of learning outcomes in basic education public schools

Statement	St. Dis		Dis		Neut		Agr		St. Ag	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Through teacher training student grades increased	5	3.2	9	6	8	5.2	78	51.6	54	35
DP learning activities improved competition	12	7.8	20	13	19	12.5	63	41	40	26
DP training of teachers increased learning performance	9	6	14	9	4	2.6	97	63	30	19.4
DP actions improved students talents	16	10.3	21	13.6	7	4.5	57	37	53	34.4
Mean	10	6.4	16	10.4	10	6.4	73.8	48	44.2	28.7

Source: Primary Data (2023).

The table 2 describes the level of learning outcomes for the students in basic education schools from the development partners' activities. During the study the majority of the respondents confirmed that developments partners activities have increased the performance of students. When respondents were asked if the training provided by development partners to teachers and students on teaching and learning activities increased the students grades, 51.6% responded agree and 35% responded strongly agree, they were asked if the development partners learning activities improved competition among teachers and students, 41% responded agree and 26% responded strongly agree, the minority were in disagreement side. They were asked if the development partners provision of training to teachers increased learning performance; 63% responded agree and 19.4% responded strongly agree. They were asked if the development partners actions improved students talents, 37% responded agree and 34.4% responded strongly agree, while the minority were in disagreement side. This means that development partner activities have improved learning outcome at higher level in basic education schools of Rwanda.

According to Taylor (2009), the research reiterate the role of development partner in education and for student learning outcomes decided the development partners strategies went far beyond that of just assigning financial means. Therefore, non-government organization are skeptical to be investors in development, suggestion were taken into account via fund transmission that the progress emerged via training and professional development processes (Taylor, 2009).

Interview responses

The respondents were asked how the development partners contribute to the students' academic outcomes in schools/ Sector and replied; "The Development partners play a distinctive role in the setting of education. As the field of education has common activities which aiming at boosting positive people lives, the partner are always sensitive in their section.

They always find some projects which may lift population welfare and wellbeing such as provision of teaching and learning materials to schools and students that have low possibilities. They also provide the support in increasing teaching methods which help education beneficiaries enjoy their services”.

The respondents were asked what they think about development partners increased school/ sector level of educational performance and replied, “Most of the development partners are interested in education sector because there are a multivariate of the activities to support and reach out to the primary beneficiaries. Most of the activities based on improving the teaching and learning process via providing some technological tools such as computers, tablets, internet, books and ebooks, health education such as mobilizing parents for fighting against malnutrition”.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher has concluded that there were various effects of the development partners in the promotion of the learning outcomes of the students in basic education schools of Kicukiro District, such as provision of the regular training to facilitate the lesson in teaching and learning, donating schools teaching and learning materials, provision of seminars to child right awareness.

The researcher has argued that development partners increased the level of learning outcomes for the students in basic education schools from the development partners’ activities such as the training provided to teachers and students on teaching and learning activities to increase the students grades, learning activities to improve competition among teachers and students and provision of training to teachers increased learning performance.

The development partners have positive influence in basic education schools where respondents were they provide services that boost education outcomes such as teaching and learning materials such as education technology devices like computers, tablets, internet, ebooks, and train the users how to use them in basic education schools of Rwanda.;

5.1 Recommendations

The results showed that the development partners play a big role in the education outcomes at high level though some activities and need more focus and need improvement in order to bring the full package contribution to the beneficiaries.

The researcher provided the following recommendations:

The Ministry of Education should be strategic to mobilize developments partners and allocate them with the areas of priorities,

The district of Kicukiro through the department partners “JADF” should identify the areas that need focus before allowing them engaging in the activities. This would help in planning for effective monitoring and evaluation,

The partners in the field of education should be able to provide support to the beneficiaries and make sure they are imparting them with required skills and knowledge in order to impact them with sustainability and self-reliance spirit.

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